

DEVELOPMENT OF ALTRUSTIC MOTIVES THROUGH LIBRARY CULTURE IN STUDENTS

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the effectiveness of the use of book reading and reading culture in the formation of altruistic behavioral motives in students, given that "the book is a grateful teacher."*

Keywords: *book, reading, altruism, moral worldview, pupil.*

In Uzbekistan, great attention is paid to the issue of moral development of young people, raising them in the spirit of humanity. In the strategic tasks of developing our country and strengthening its independence proposed by our President Sh.M.Mirziyev, the volunteer, national pride, who can help the society in solving social tasks, training mentally mature, competent generation and competitive personnel is predominant. Education of young people is defined as one of the important tasks. In the implementation of these tasks, "we rely on our national traditions formed over the centuries, the rich heritage of our ancestors" [1; p. 48] and educating the growing young generation in the spirit of universal human values built on the basis of Eastern education lays a huge responsibility on the society.

Of course, the role of school education is incomparable in solving these tasks. In this regard, the leader of the country emphasizes to the school teachers the issue of formation of reading culture in students, which is one of the national characteristics. The famous literary scholar and translator Azod Sharafiddinov, who was honored as the owner of spiritual courage, defined the seven wonders of the world and said, "... seven wonders are the fiery hymn of the human mind, thinking, heart, and the eternal monument dedicated to the greatness of human genius. is happening. However, despite this, there is another miracle in the world, whose greatness and sanctity are no less than the total glory and beauty of the seven miracles. This miracle is a book. "Many great people have noted that the book is a miracle, even if it is a miracle, it is the first miracle." For example, the writer and dramatist S. Sveig said, "Where there is a book, there a person does not remain in peace with himself, within his scope, to all the universal achievements of the past and the present, to the thoughts and ideas of all mankind. he will be familiar with his feelings", he writes. Writer and philosopher J. Swift said, "Books are the children of the mind," pedagogue and writer Y. Comensky said, "Books are a tool for spreading wisdom," and philosopher and historian F. Bacon said, "Books float in the waves of time and pass on their precious burden from generations." - are ships of thought that are passed down to generations," he writes. In this way, great scholars, sages, writers and scientists likened the book to a miracle, a light, a pillar of thought, a symbol of eternity and spirituality, a source of knowledge, a faithful friend, a mirror of time. Above all, the book is an invincible force in the fight against ignorance with enlightenment.

There are many proverbs in the language of our people about the importance of acquiring knowledge and proper upbringing, learning a profession by reading books. For example, "A mind without a book is a bird without wings", "Knowledge is a lamp of the mind", "Beauty is knowledge in enlightenment". Such wise sayings can be continued for a long time. An important factor that

has been showing people the right path for thousands of years, making them educated, educated, professional and of course happy is to be friends with books and not to hate reading books. Books have a special place in the lives of young people. Because a good book increases a person's feelings of love for the Motherland, respect for national and universal values, and encourages goodness and goodness. One of the motives of hidden goodness in the books is altruism.

The concept of altruism is derived from the Latin word "alter" - "others" and was introduced into science by the French philosopher O. Comte as a term opposite to egoism. Altruism is an activity aimed at showing unselfish care to other people for their benefit [4; p. 6]. Studies aimed at studying the motives of altruism have been conducted in three directions within all scientific fields. These are: a) the direction of learning as a criterion of moral behavior based on D. Wright's views; b) research direction based on the research of L. Kolberg and T. Laikon as the highest example of personal development; c) Research in the direction of perfect human characteristics based on the ideas of Eastern scholars and philosophers. After all, in all of these areas, altruism is considered as the highest peak of acmeological development of a person [2; p. 465]. The peak of this acmeological development can be reached through reading culture. For example, J. Rumi's "In the end we will be dust: from the wisdom of "Masnavii is spiritual"", "Makhbub ul-Qulub" by A. Navoi, "Khamsa", "The days of the past" by A. Qadiri. If we take the works of Mehrobdan Chayan", T. Malik's "Human Property", Oibek's "Navoiy", the legends "To'maris", "Shirok", we can find images promoting the ideas of altruism in all of them.

Scholars of the East made a great contribution to the development of the world with their rare works. Therefore, if we read their works, we will come across pedagogical and psychological views related to all fields. Among other things, we can witness the systematic elucidation of altruism motives based on the science of futuvat. If you read Alisher Navoi's work "Makhbub ul-Qulub", one of the great scholars of the East, you will see the oriental description of altruistic behavior: "Generosity is a fruitful tree of the garden of personality, but it is also a sweet fruit of the tree; the wave, the river of the land of civilization, perhaps it is the original jewel of the wave river. Kindness, cabbage - is to bear the burden of hardship of a victim and save from those difficulties. Cabbage is to bear the weight of someone's hard thorn and to open like a flower from the tip of the thorn and not to mention the work done, not to take it into one's mouth, not to thank the person and not to put it in his face. Muruvvat is a descendant of the good cabbage, a twin relative, whoever has these qualities will be honored and respected" [3; pp. 92-95]. Such descriptions are also widely found in the works of Farobi, Beruni, Rumi, Koshifi, A. Avloni. By reading and studying these sources, students can develop not only altruistic motives, but also feelings of national pride, pride, and patriotism.

Ideas of behavior based on altruistic motives are also reflected in the views of modern literature. For example, let's take the image of Yusufbek Khoji in A. Qadiri's novel "Past Days". The author of the work himself called Yusufbek Khoja "... a selfless person who cares about the interests of the people and the country" [6; 5-p.], defines that. Through this image, A. Qadiri considered fighting for the unity of the nation, the integrity of the Motherland as the meaning of his life; if the situation continues in this way, by encouraging the petty people who are quarreling with each other due to nepotism, familiarity, and localism; describes the great figure who prophesied the destruction of the nation, the humiliation of the land under the feet of the conquerors. It is obvious that altruistic motives are hidden behind the behavior of this "sacrifice of

the nation". Because we can see that higher values prevail over personal interests in the moral outlook of this character.

Let's take the story "The Last Victim of War" by our favorite writer O'tkir Hashimov. The story creates the imagination of the students that the war took place not only on the front lines, but also in every village, every household, and the victims of the war were found in every family [5; p. 160]. In addition, it is stated that even though the hero of the work, Shoikrom, did not go to war, he had to suffer his horror and bitterness at home. The only cow used by the family was stolen, the brother is seriously ill and bedridden, and as if this was not enough, the last food of the children - a handful of strawberries at the edge of the yard - was stolen. Inadequacy and selfishness force Shoikrom to make a shaky decision. Shoikrom's selfishness creates a sad situation. Through the sad fate of the hero of the work, it is taught to the students what the consequences of not getting information about the condition of their loved ones and not helping them will be as a result of living surrounded by their own problems. Through the plot of events in the story, the author encourages readers to avoid selfishness, be altruistic, and be devoted to their loved ones.

In general, if we conclude on the basis of the above points:

1. Reading culture among students serves to increase their spiritual worldview and moral consciousness.
2. We can observe the manifestation of altruistic motives based on the science of benevolence in the works of Eastern scholars and legends;
3. Altruism is one of the national characteristics based on giving selfless help to others;
4. It is possible to form altruistic behavior motives in students by promoting the reading of literary works in coaching hours in schools.

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